

POPS 0307 Final Certification

Field	Mean +/- STD [actual range]	Pass/Fail
Zero Cnts (#/s)	0.02 ± 0.13 [0.00 - 1.00]	PASS
Flow (ccs)	2.97 ± 0.10 [2.53 - 3.14]	PASS
Baseline (counts)	2022 ± 1.05 [2020 - 2024]	PASS
STD (counts)	10.46 ± 0.49 [9.31 - 11.83]	PASS
Pressure (mbar)	837.99 ± 0.04 [837.92 - 838.09]	PASS
BoardTemp (C)	34.62 ± 0.04 [34.57 - 34.72]	PASS
LDTemp (C)	44.78 ± 0.06 [44.44 - 44.95]	PASS
Temp (C)	23.52 ± 0.08 [23.26 - 23.94]	PASS
BatV (V)	11.31 ± 0.01 [11.23 - 11.32]	PASS

